

Standardizing Metadata for Environmental Microplastics Research

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Sept. 27, 2021

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A situation to avoid

Challenges Remain in Combining Data from Multiple Organizations

Since 1899, nutrient records collected by

488

agencies / organizations

at

321,927

stream sites

for a total of

25 million nutrient records

14.5 million of these nutrient records had missing or ambiguous information that limited their use for regional or national assessments

“At current costs, the nutrient records with **missing or ambiguous reference information represent an estimated \$12 billion worth of data** that are unavailable for regional or national analyses by secondary data users.”

US Geological Survey

https://acwi.gov/nawqa/NLCmeetings/multisource_data.pdf
Sprague, Oelsner, Argue *Water Research* **2017**, 110, 252-261

Coming soon to a lab near you

Government
of Canada

Gouvernement
du Canada

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Research Data Management

Tri-Agency Statement of
Principles on Digital Data

Tri-Agency Research Data Management Policy

4. Implementation dates

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- *Institutional strategies:* **By March 1, 2023**, research institutions subject to this requirement must post their RDM strategies and notify the agencies when they have been completed.
- *Data management plans:* **By spring 2022**, the agencies will identify the initial set of funding opportunities subject to the DMP requirement. The agencies will pilot the DMP requirement in targeted funding opportunities before this date.
- *Data deposit:* After reviewing the institutional strategies and in line with the readiness of the Canadian research community, the agencies will phase in the deposit requirement.

https://www.science.gc.ca/eic/site/063.nsf/eng/h_97610.html

Create metadata template for general use in environmental (water and sediments) microplastics research projects.

- adapt existing metadata schemas
- engaging microplastics researchers, stakeholders and RDM practitioners
- establish an ongoing dialogue to adapt to the inevitable evolution of microplastics research

“**To minimize barriers to data exchange**, the format of data and metadata should be compatible with **national or international database structures**. In particular, the **global water quality database GEMStat** (<https://gemstat.org>) can serve as an example. It should be noted that plastic is currently not in the GEMStat parameter list, although its inclusion is under consideration.”

Monitoring Plastics in Rivers and Lakes: Guidelines for the Harmonization of Methodologies
UN Environment Programme (2020)

<https://wedocs.unep.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.11822/35405/MPRL.pdf>

Arctic Monitoring & Assessment Programme

<https://litterandmicroplastics.amap.no/>

UN Environment Programme

<https://www.unep.org/resources/report/microplastics>

US Environmental Protection Agency

Water Quality Exchange Web Template Files

Note About Template Files

The templates are made up of two Microsoft Excel spreadsheet files that are meant to be used together to assist with data tracking and entry. The WQX Web Template Dictionary file provides guidance on the appropriate use of each data element, highlighting the data elements that are available in the WQX Web Template and showing the additional data elements that a user may add to the template. The dictionary covers data elements for all templates including:

- Physical-Chemical Results
- Biological Results
- Habitat Results, Activity Metrics and Indices
- Continuous Monitoring Results
- Lab Results

Many of the templates contain sample data that can be imported into WQX Web using the following import configurations (for more information regarding how to use Import Configuration files in WQX Web, please see the WQX web tutorials).

<https://www.epa.gov/waterdata/water-quality-exchange-web-template-files>

Academic Literature

W. Cowger et al. *Appl. Spectr.* **2020**, *74*, 1066-1077.

	Number of elements	Percent of total
From DataStream & WQX	36	21%
From WQX	33	19%
New proposed	101	59%
Total elements from WQX	69	41%
Total elements in template	170	100%

“Use metadata are describing the actual content of a dataset and how it is encoded.
The purpose is to **enable the user to understand the data without any further communication.**
It describes content of variables using **standardized vocabularies**, units of variable, encoding of missing values, map projections etc”

- Review template (in excel) and provide your feedback on suite of variables identify
- Beta testing users

MP Field sampling (metadata)

Yellow text: mandatory on DataStream
White text: optional on DataStream
Red text: WQX only

Glassware cleaning method should be described

Report suppliers of labware, consumables, chemicals, and instruments

For labware, report relevant material properties (glass, plastic, etc.) and sizes/volumes

Conditional

Sample processing methods recommended for water

For labware, report relevant material properties (glass, plastic, etc.) and sizes/volumes

Where relevant, specify quantities of consumables used

Describe method used to clean glassware

Report method for filtering reagents

Material of clothing and gloves used in the lab should be described

Report suppliers of labware, consumables, and chemicals.

Share raw data and analysis code as often as possible

Describe contaminant devices used (e.g. flow hoods, glove bags)

Result Analytical Method

Chemical

Pyrolysis gas chromatography mass spectrometry

Raman spectroscopy

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy

Differential scanning calorimetry

- Spectral matching parameters
- Pre-processing parameters
- Acquisition parameters

- Acquisition parameters
- Pre-processing parameters
- Matching parameters

- Acquisition parameters
- Matching parameters

- Pyrolysis
- Gas separation parameters
- MS acquisition parameters
- Matching criteria
- Quantification techniques

- Pyrolysis temperature
- Pyrolysis duration time
- Volume of the chemical
- Concentration of chemical
- Compare characteristic peaks with literature
- Use software to compare average mass spectrum with a library

Visual

Image settings

Light microscopy

Fluorescence microscopy

Scanning electron microscopy

- settings for light
- Magnification

- contrast
- saturation
- Light intensity
- grain

- Add scale bar to images
- Description of magnification used during assessment

- Magnification used during identification
- Shapes, colours, textures, and reflectance used for identification

- Magnification used during identification
- Light wavelength, intensity, and exposure time to light
- Threshold intensity (maximum and minimum value)

- Coating used
- Magnification used during identification
- Textures used for identification

- Gas pressure/vapor content
- EDS measurement (if taken)
- Conductivity of sample

- Report suppliers of labware, consumables, chemicals, and instruments
- Report how instruments and software are calibrated
- Share raw data and analysis code as often as possible

Standardized shape categories
[GESAMP: Pg. 11, Table 2.3]

Common sizes identified by measurable units
[GESAMP: Pg 10, Table 2.2]

Standardized texture descriptions
[Textures: Section 3]

12-colours classification (ISCC-NBS)
or
8-colour classification (EMODnet)
Method used to determine and classify colour should be discussed.
[GESAMP: Pg. 12]

Standardized polymer definitions
[GESAMP: Pg. 6]

Is there a library of polymer choices that can used?

Textures: https://www.surfacesciencwestern.com/pdf/0909_mpb09_biesinger.pdf

GESAMP Guidance Document: <http://www.gesamp.org/publications/guidelines-for-the-monitoring-and-assessment-of-plastic-litter-in-the-ocean>

Discovery level (metadata)

Used to find relevant data once it is a repository

Suggest ISO 19115 metadata schema as DataStream and metadata fields also fits in well with:

- Federated Research Repository
- Polar Data Catalogue
- Open Government Metadata

Title of dataset

Dataset Abstract

Responsible person (s) & Affiliation & Orcid

Study site name and coordinates

Topic Category

Keywords

at least five- must include “**microplastics**”

Data citation

Time period data was collected

Data security

Funding

Licensing & Attribution

Maintenance Frequency

Common to FRDR & DS

Data Stream only